

Teachers' Perspective and Instructional Implementation of Modular Distance Learning during the Pandemic

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to assess the perspectives and instructional implementation of public elementary school teachers in the context of modular distance learning. A quantitative descriptive research design using a survey technique was employed. The respondents of this study were the 87 elementary school teachers of District II of the Department of Education-Surigao City Division. The main instrument used in this study was a researcher-made questionnaire. The statistical tools used in this study were Frequency Count and Percentage Distribution, Mean and Standard Deviation, and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. It was concluded that the teachers highly valued modular distance learning as they have positive feelings about this modality, interacted or behaved well towards its implementation, and believed in the importance of the modality during this pandemic. Moreover, the teachers were doing well in their implementation of modular distance learning during the pandemic in terms of crafting, producing, distributing, and retrieving modules, feedbacking, giving remediation, and doing home visitation. The way how the teacher felt, interacted, behaved, thought, and behaved about modular distance learning were related to how they implemented instruction, thus, the affect, behavior, and cognition were related to instructional implementation. It was hereby recommended that the school administrators may implement projects, programs, and activities that would enhance the skills of their teachers in implementing modular distance learning especially in giving remediation and feedback.

Keywords: affect, behavior, cognition, instructional implementation, modular distance learning

INTRODUCTION

Education Secretary Briones (2020) says, "Education must continue even in times of crisis, whether it may be a calamity, disaster, emergency, quarantine, or even war." With the global crisis that is happening, many sectors were greatly affected. Educational institutions were challenged as to how they will deliver instruction in these trying times. In this sense, the Department of Education came up with a Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan where it laid out the plans to continue education by employing different learning modalities. One of these is the distance learning delivery modality.

Distance learning, as defined in the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan in the Time of COVID-19 (2020) of the Department of Education, refers to a learning delivery modality where learning occurs between the teacher and the learners. They are geographically distant from each other during instruction. Under this mode of learning, there are three types: Modular Distance Learning (MDL), Online Distance Learning (ODL), and television (TV)/Radio-Based Instruction. According to Bernardo (2020), learning through printed and digital modules emerged as the most preferred distance

Received: 29 Sept. 2022

Revised: 13 Oct. 2022

Final Accepted for publication: 22 Oct 2022

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learning method for parents. Based on a survey conducted by the Department of Education (DepEd), 8.9 million parents preferred modular distance learning, where students at home would study through self-learning modules.

The Department of Education – Division of Surigao City uses Modular Distance Learning in most public elementary schools. It offers printed or digital self-learning modules where the pupils, with the guidance of the parents, go through the lessons with related activities.

The researchers were prompted to conduct this study to assess the perspectives and instructional implementation of Modular Distance Learning in District II of Surigao City Division under the new normal. It also determined the relationship between the perspectives and the implementation of the teacher. Enhancement of instructional implementation in modular distance learning may be proposed based on the findings of the study.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The researchers used a quantitative descriptive survey research design to gather information regarding the perspectives and level of instructional implementation of the respondents on Modular Distance Learning. Shuttleworth (2008) defined a descriptive research design as a valid method for researching specific subjects and as a precursor to more quantitative studies. In this sense, this design was deemed appropriate for this kind of study because it looked into a specific subject, Modular Distance Learning, and it also involved the collection of data to test the hypothesis.

The respondents of this study were the 87 elementary school teachers of District II of the Department of Education-Surigao City Division. The respondents were selected through random sampling. The sample size was determined using Slovin's Formula.

The main instrument used in this study was a researcher-made questionnaire. The questionnaire consisted of three (3) parts. Part 1 was about the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, civil status, grade levels taught, length of service, highest educational attainment, and subjects handled. Part 2 of the questionnaire was about the teachers' perspectives towards modular distance learning. Part 3 was about the instructional implementation under modular distance learning. The questionnaire underwent validation by experts and reliability tests. The Cronbach alpha is 0.97 which means that the internal consistency is excellent.

In determining the teachers' perspectives and level of instructional implementation in modular distance learning, the following statistical tools were utilized to analyze the data. Frequency Count and Percentage Distribution were used to describe the respondents' profile in terms of age, sex, civil status, grade levels taught, length of service, highest educational attainment, and subjects handled. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to determine the teachers' perspectives and level of instructional implementation in modular distance learning. Pearson Product Moment Correlation of Coefficient was used to test the significant relationship between the teachers' perspectives and the level of the implementation in modular distance learning, as well as the profile and the respondents' perspectives and instructional implementation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This study aimed to assess the perspectives and instructional implementation of public elementary school teachers in the context of modular distance learning. A quantitative descriptive research design using a survey technique was employed. The respondents of

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this study were the 87 elementary school teachers of District II of the Department of Education-Surigao City Division. The main instrument used in this study was a researcher-made questionnaire. The statistical tools used in this study were Frequency Count and Percentage Distribution, Mean and Standard Deviation, and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient.

Based on the analysis done on the data gathered, the findings revealed in this study are summarized as follows:

1. In terms of *age*, 15 (17.24%) participants belong to the 35-39 and 55-59 years old bracket, then 40-44 years old with 13 (14.94%), 30-34 years old with 12 (13.79%), 25-29 and 50-54 years old with 11 (12.64%), 45-49 years old with 8 (9.20%), and 60-64 years old with 2 (2.30%). In terms of *sex*, most of the participants are females with 80 (91.95%) while 7 (8.05%) are males. In terms of *civil status*, most of the participants are married with 68 (78.16%), then 17 (19.54%) are single, and 1 (1.15%) separated and widowed, respectively.

In terms of the *grade level taught*, there are 15 participants (17.24%) who are teaching in Grade 3, then 14 (16.09%) are teaching Grade 1 and Grade 5, respectively, 11 (12.64%) are teaching Kindergarten, Grade 2 and Grade 6, respectively, 10 (11.49%) are teaching in Grade 4, and 1 (1.15%) is teaching in ALS.

In terms of the *number of years in service*, there are 21 (24.14%) participants who served for 6-10 years, then 17 (19.54%) served for 11-15 years, 15 (17.24%) served for 1-5 years, 10 (11.49%) served for 21-25 years, 9 (10.34%) served for 26-30 years, 7 (8.05%) served for 16-20 years, 6 (6.90%) served for 31-35 years, and 2 (2.30%) served for 36-40 years.

In terms of *highest educational attainment*, more than half of the participants have MA units with 55 (63.22%), then 17 (19.54%) attained a college degree, 11 (12.64%) attained a master's degree, and 2 (2.30%) earned Ph.D. units and attained doctorate, respectively.

In terms of *subject/s handled*, 74 (17.21%) are handling ESP, 63 (14.65%) are handling English, 60 (13.95%) are handling Filipino, 58 (13.49%) are handling Math and MAPEH, respectively, 48 (11.16%) are handling MTB-MLE, 37 (8.60%) are handling Science, 12 (2.79%) are handling TLE, 11 (2.56%) are handling Kindergarten Subjects, and 9 (2.09%) are handling Araling Panlipunan.

2. The respondents' perspective toward modular distance learning in terms of *affect* is verbally interpreted as *always* and qualitatively described as *highly valued* ($\underline{M}=3.31$, $SD=0.69$). This means that teachers highly value modular distance learning as they have positive feelings about this learning modality. The item *I feel proud because I was able to craft self-directed activities for my learners* got the highest mean ($\underline{M}=3.49$, $SD=0.66$), which can be verbally interpreted as *always* and qualitatively described as *highly valued*. Meanwhile, the item *I do not worry about the preparation, distribution, and retrieval of modules* got the lowest mean ($\underline{M}=3.09$, $SD=0.73$), which can be verbally interpreted as *often* and qualitatively described as *moderately valued*.

It can be noted that the teachers were happy because the resources were provided to the teachers and schools to implement modular distance learning fully and were motivated to design self-learning modules. This is true because the district and division at-large administrators are working hand-in-hand to support the teachers in implementing modular distance learning.

The respondents' perspective toward modular distance learning in terms of *behavior* is verbally interpreted as *always* and qualitatively described as *highly valued* ($\underline{M}=3.60$, $SD=0.50$). This means that the teachers interact or behave well towards the implementation of modular distance learning as they highly value this learning modality. The item *I am open to new educational practices in modular distance learning* got the highest mean ($\underline{M}=3.72$, $SD=0.45$), which can be verbally interpreted as *always* and qualitatively described as *highly valued*. Meanwhile, the item *I have helped others in crafting varied activities that are appropriate to this situation* got the lowest mean ($\underline{M}=3.51$, $SD=0.55$), which can be verbally interpreted as *always* and qualitatively described as *highly valued*.

The new normal in Philippine public education, as found out by Jamon et al. (2021), showed resilience among the teachers despite the weaknesses and threats and translated those into strengths and opportunities. In the educational landscape, according to Tria (2020), the new normal should be taken into consideration to sustain and provide quality education despite the crisis; thus, there is a need to plan and implement the "new normal educational policy."

The respondents' perspective toward modular distance learning in terms of *cognition* is verbally interpreted as *always* and qualitatively described as *highly valued* ($\underline{M}=3.37$, $SD=0.59$). This means that the teachers believed in the importance of modular distance learning during this pandemic as they highly valued this learning modality. The items *I have considered feedbacking an essential part of my learner's growth, especially when no face-to-face classes are held*, and *In modular distance learning, coordination and communication with both the parents and students must be consistently done* got the highest means ($\underline{M}=3.55$, $SD=0.52$ and 0.57 , respectively), which can be verbally interpreted as *always* and qualitatively described as *highly valued*. Meanwhile, the item *In modular distance learning, the learners learn independently and at their own pace with minimal supervision and guidance from the teacher* got the lowest mean ($\underline{M}=3.06$, $SD=0.67$), which can be verbally interpreted as *often* and qualitatively described as *moderately valued*.

San Antonio (2020), in his memorandum, suggested that monitoring of learner's progress and setting up of feedback mechanisms shall be ensured to help them meet the targeted competencies while looking into the connection of one lesson to the next for the coherence of the curriculum; and timely and appropriate monitoring and feedback for intervention and consultation purposes shall be put in place through various media such as text messaging, and audio/video calls, whichever is accessible to the learner. Moreover, intervention is also important as Arpilleda (2021) found that the use of intervention materials gave a positive impact in mastering the least-learned competencies.

3. The respondents' level of instructional implementation in modular distance learning is verbally interpreted as *always* and qualitatively described as *highly implemented* ($\underline{M}=3.45$, $SD=0.60$). This means that the teachers are doing well in their implementation of modular distance learning during the pandemic from crafting, producing, distributing, and retrieving modules, feedbacking, giving remediation, and doing home visitation. The item *I respond to the learners who need assistance via email, telephone, text message/ instant messaging* got the highest mean ($\underline{M}=3.66$, $SD=0.48$), which can be verbally interpreted as *always* and qualitatively described as *highly implemented*. Meanwhile, the item *I do home visits to learners needing remediation or assistance* got the lowest mean ($\underline{M}=3.14$,

SD=0.78), which can be verbally interpreted as *often* and qualitatively described as *moderately implemented*.

In modular distance learning, the teacher is responsible for monitoring the learners' progress. The learners may ask for assistance from the teacher via email, telephone, text message/instant messaging, etc. (DO No. 12, s. 2020). In addition, San Antonio (2020), in his memorandum, suggested that timely and appropriate monitoring and feedback for intervention and consultation purposes shall be put in place through various media such as text messaging and audio/video calls, whichever is accessible to the learner.

4. As to the correlation between the respondents' perspective and instructional implementation in modular distance learning, findings revealed that there is a *moderate positive correlation* between the respondents' perspective in terms of *affect* and their *instructional implementation* (r-value=0.51); there is a *high positive correlation* between the respondents' perspective in terms of *behavior* and their *instructional implementation* (r-value=0.71), and *cognition* and their *instructional implementation* (r-value=0.72). There is a significant correlation between the respondents' perspectives in terms of *affect*, *behavior*, and *cognition* and *instructional implementation* in modular distance learning (p-value=0.000, 0.000, 0.000, respectively). Since there is a moderate to high positive correlation, it implies that when the value of one variable increases or decreases, the value of the other variable increases or decreases, respectively, in a similar fashion. Based on the results, given the positive correlation, it means that when the teachers' perspective towards modular distance learning is high, their implementation is also high; otherwise, when the perspective is low, the implementation is also low.

Sener (2015) discovered that more positive teacher attitudes are linked to teaching success. Teachers with positive attitudes can build positive relationships in the classroom, generate positive energy, and make the learning process easier, improving teaching quality. The result is similar to Khan (2017), who found out that the instructional beliefs of the teacher educators were significantly correlated with their classroom practices. However, in this study, beliefs refer to the cognition of the respondents. Having extensive knowledge and strong beliefs do not ensure the practice of such, but attitudes, whether negative or positive, are drivers of action or practice (Arpilleda and Mallillin, 2020).

5. As to the relationship between the respondents' *age* and their perspective in terms of *affect*, *behavior*, and *cognition* and their *instructional implementation* in modular distance learning, findings revealed that there is a *negligible correlation* between these variables (r-values=-0.02, -0.09, 0.05, 0.05, respectively). There is no significant relationship between the respondents' *age* and their perspective in terms of *affect*, *behavior*, and *cognition* and their *instructional implementation* in modular distance learning (p-value=0. 0.857, 0.384, 0.672, 0.624, respectively).

As to the relationship between the respondents' *sex* and their perspective in terms of *affect*, *behavior*, and *cognition* and their *instructional implementation* in modular distance learning, findings revealed that there is a *negligible correlation* between these variables (r-values=0.07, 0.00, 0.08, 0.10, respectively). There is no significant relationship between the respondents' *sex* and their perspective in terms of *affect*, *behavior*, and *cognition* and their *instructional implementation* in modular distance learning (p-value=0.508, 0.974, 0.461, 0.359, respectively).

As to the relationship between the respondents' *civil status* and their perspective in terms of *affect*, *behavior*, and *cognition* and their *instructional implementation* in modular distance learning, findings revealed that there is a *negligible correlation* between these

variables (r -values=0.09, 0.01, 0.12, 0.08, respectively). There is no significant relationship between the respondents' *civil status* and their perspective in terms of *affect*, *behavior*, and *cognition* and their *instructional implementation* in modular distance learning (p -value=0.403, 0.925, 0.259, 0.488, respectively).

As to the relationship between the respondents' *grade level taught* and their perspective in terms of *affect*, *behavior*, and *cognition* and their *instructional implementation* in modular distance learning, findings revealed that there is a *negligible correlation* between these variables (r -values=0.00, 0.03, 0.10, 0.10, respectively). There is no significant relationship between the respondents' *grade level taught* and their perspective in terms of *affect*, *behavior*, and *cognition* and their *instructional implementation* in modular distance learning (p -value=0.978, 0.786, 0.338, 0.357, respectively).

As to the relationship between the respondents' *length of service* and their perspective in terms of *affect*, *behavior*, and *cognition* and their *instructional implementation* in modular distance learning, findings revealed that there is a *negligible correlation* between these variables (r -values=-0.04, -0.12, 0.02, 0.03, respectively). There is no significant relationship between the respondents' *length of service* and their perspective in terms of *affect*, *behavior*, and *cognition* and their *instructional implementation* in modular distance learning (p -value=0.719, 0.282, 0.873, 0.807, respectively).

As to the relationship between the respondents' *subject/s handled* and their perspective in terms of *affect*, *behavior*, and *cognition* and their *instructional implementation* in modular distance learning, findings revealed that there is a *negligible correlation* between these variables (r -values=0.03, 0.04, 0.00, -0.03, respectively). There is no significant relationship between the respondents' *subject/s handled* and their perspective in terms of *affect*, *behavior*, and *cognition* and their *instructional implementation* (p -value=0.771, 0.709, 0.994, 0.785, respectively).

As to the relationship between the respondents' *highest educational attainment* and their perspective in terms of *affect*, *behavior*, and *cognition* and their *instructional implementation* in modular distance learning, findings revealed that there is a *negligible correlation* between these variables (r -values=0.02, 0.13, 0.06, 0.15, respectively). There is no significant relationship between the respondents' *highest educational attainment* and their perspective in terms of *affect*, *behavior*, and *cognition* and their *instructional implementation* in modular distance learning (p -value=0.850, 0.225, 0.563, 0.177, respectively).

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings revealed in this study, the researchers concluded that (1) The teachers highly valued modular distance learning as they have positive feelings about this modality, interact or behave well towards its implementation, and believe in the importance of the modality during this pandemic; (2) The teachers were doing well in their implementation of modular distance learning during the pandemic in terms of crafting, producing, distributing, and retrieving modules, feedbacking, giving remediation, and doing home visitation; (3) The way how the teacher feels, interacts, behaves, thinks, and behaves about modular distance learning were related to how they implement instruction, thus, the affect, behavior, and cognition were related to instructional implementation; and (4) The teachers' age, sex, civil status, grade levels taught, length of service, highest educational attainment, and subjects handled were not related to their perspectives on modular distance learning.

Acknowledgements

We wish to convey our heartfelt gratitude to the elementary school teachers of District II of the Department of Education-Surigao City Division for their participation in the conduct of the study. We would also like to thank the District II of the Department of Education-Surigao City Division for allowing us to conduct this study, along with the administration, faculty and staff.

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Received: 29 Sept. 2022

Revised: 13 Oct. 2022

Final Accepted for publication: 22 Oct 2022

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